

**SIZE-EFFECT INDEPENDENCE OF
PARTICLEBOARD FRACTURE TOUGHNESS**

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ABSTRACT

The present paper aims to prove the size-effect independence of particleboard (PB) fracture toughness when the Modified Two-Parameter Model (MTPM), recently proposed by some of the present authors, is used to measure such a parameter. Firstly, three-point bending (TPB) tests on single-edge notched specimens characterised by three different values of thickness are performed for a commercial particleboard. By exploiting such experimental data, the value of the fracture toughness is analytically determined through the MTPM. Then,

a fracture toughness index is defined by taking into account the dependence of fracture toughness on the material density. Finally, the mean value of such an index is compared with that obtained from the results (available in the literature) related to a previous experimental campaign performed on the same commercial PB.

KEYWORDS: fracture toughness; Modified Two-Parameter Model; particleboard; size-independent; wood-based composite.

NOMENCLATURE

a_0	notch depth
B	specimen width (corresponding to the panel thickness)
B_c	Specimen coating thickness
B_{Core}	Specimen core thickness
B_f	Specimen faces thickness
C_i	initial linear elastic compliance
C_u	unloading linear elastic compliance
E	elastic modulus
I_K	fracture toughness index
K_{IC}	critical Stress-Intensity Factor for Mode I
K_{IIC}	critical Stress-Intensity Factor for Mode II
$K_{IC,eq}$	critical equivalent Stress-Intensity Factor for mixed mode
$K_{(I+II)C}^S$	critical Stress-Intensity Factor for mixed mode
L	specimen length

P applied load
 P_{\max} peak load
 S support span
 v CMOD rate
 W specimen depth
 ρ particleboard density

ACRONYMS

PB particleboard
CMOD Crack Mouth Opening Displacement
MTPM Modified Two-Parameter Model
SIF Stress-Intensity Factor
TPM Two-Parameter Model

1. INTRODUCTION

Wood-based composite is a general term for a large variety of products, mainly consisting of wood elements (particles, fibres, strands, and veneers) bonded together by thermosetting adhesives. According to the form of such elements, the wood-based composites may be classified as: particleboard (PB), medium or high density-fibreboard (MDF or HDF), oriented strand board (OSB), and plywood.

In particular, PBs are manufactured as panels made of dry wood particles, sprayed or dusted with a binder resin and compressed by high pressure at high temperature [1]. Each panel is typically

consisting of three layers (**Figure 1**). The two outer layers (named faces) are made of fine wood particles with a resin content ranging from 8% to 15%, whereas the inner layer (named core) is made of coarser particles with a resin content ranging from 4% to 8% [1]. Coatings may complete the PB panel.

Figure 1

The production of the panels in such a layered structure optimizes the use of the raw material, and the smooth faces present a suitable surface for laminating, overlaying, painting, and veneering [1]. The thickness of each layer may vary depending on many factors such as: the wood type, the forming process, the total thickness of the panel, and so on.

In 2010, the share of particleboards in the overall wood-based panel production was around 63% [2]. The majority of the ligno-cellulosic material used for the PB production is wood from forest [3]. However, in some European countries, the use of wood waste, especially coming from industrial activities, has significantly increased in recent years, reaching a maximum share of 40% [4,5]. In addition to wood, alternative raw materials have been added to improve the quality of PBs, such as cotton [6], bark [7], sugar cane bagasse [8], rice husk [9], and so on.

PBs are currently employed in many industry and civil engineering applications. Their commercial success may be attributed to their dimensional stability, uniform properties, good load bearing capacity,

and low cost with respect to the solid wood, in addition to a better resistance to degradation due to fungi, bacteria and insects [10].

According to the European Standards, the structural performance of wood-based composites (such as PBs) may be assessed by tension testing [11,12], bending testing [13], and Internal Bond (IB) testing (to measure the tension strength in the core layer perpendicular to the faces) [11,12]. Note that bending and IB tests are usually performed by the panel producers for quality assurance of the whole production chain [14,15].

Fracture in solid wood and wood-based composites takes place in two main steps: crack initiation and crack propagation [16]. During crack initiation, a process zone is formed containing numerous micro-cracks, which join together to form a macro-crack. During the propagation phase, such a process zone continuously moves ahead the tip of the macro-crack. In the weak zone, behind the crack tip, bridging effects may take place due to the unbroken wood particles. In both wood and wood-based products, the process zone is usually large compared with the typical laboratory-scale specimen sizes [16].

By examining the state of the art, studies on fracture in solid wood and wood-based composites show that Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) approaches exploiting fracture toughness were widely applied in the past [16]. Nowadays, it is commonly accepted that wood and its products may be treated as quasi-brittle materials for which a Non-Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (NLEFM) approach is recommended [16, 17].

Experience in non-wood quasi-brittle materials suggests that fracture toughness tests provide an accurate and reliable characterisation of both fracture and mechanical performance rather than strength tests [18,19]. While a single value of fracture toughness is appropriate for brittle materials, a resistance curve (R-curve) is needed for quasi-brittle ones (as PBs) to take into account that the fracture resistance increases with crack extension, promoting stable crack growth before the load peak is reached. Note that, to determine the R-curve, specimens with same geometric sizes but different notch depths are needed. Dourado et al. [20] performed three-point bending (TPB) fracture measurements on notched prismatic specimens made of pine and spruce wood. The obtained load-displacement curves were used to determine the Resistance-curves by employing an equivalent linear elastic approach. Double Cantilever Beams (DCB), usually employed for the characterisation of material fracture behaviour [21,22], were commonly used also for wood composites [23-25]. Gagliano and Frazier proposed to use double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens and the "corrected compliance" method for the analysis of wooden materials [23]. In such a case, the specimens made of solid wood and plywood are subjected to Mode I cleavage testing, and the crack lengths are monitored during the tests by using a camera. Other Authors, such as Lavischi et al. [24] and Yoshihara [25], have performed fracture energy tests on DCB specimens of various geometrical shapes. In Ref. [24], the test method described by Gagliano and Frazier [23] is applied to DCB specimens made of solid

wood and plywood in order to estimate the fracture energy. Yoshihara [25] used specimens made of medium density fiberboard to perform DCB tests and TPB tests, in order to obtain Mode I and Mode II fracture toughnesses. Further investigations have highlighted that the main problem of the methods employing DCB specimens is the accuracy in measuring the crack length during the tests [26-28].

Another methodology to analyse the fracture behaviour of wood and wood-based materials was developed by Stanzl-Tschegg et al. [29] using the wedge splitting method. Such a method, originally proposed by Tschegg [30] for inhomogeneous materials such as concrete, allows us to obtain the fracture energy from integration of the load-displacement curve which can be determined forcing the specimen to fail by pure opening Mode [29,30].

By focusing the attention on particleboards, Beer et al. [31,32] determined the fracture energy through microtome cutting tests, and compared their results with those obtained from wedge splitting tests. Veigel et al. [27] studied the fracture behaviour of various PBs made of different adhesives reinforced with cellulose nanofibres, by employing DCB specimens. Marsavina et al. [33] investigated both Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness of a commercial PB by testing single-edge notched bend specimens and compact shear specimens, respectively.

Vantadori et al. [34] have recently proposed the Modified Two-Parameter Model (MTPM), which may be applied to any material characterised by a quasi-brittle behaviour. Such a model is based on the Two-Parameter Model (TPM) developed by Jenq and Shah [35] for

plain concrete, which was able to determine a size-independent Mode I fracture toughness by accounting for the non-linear crack growth before the peak load is reached in three-point bending tests. The model allows us to take into account the stable crack propagation by computing the fracture toughness using the effective crack length instead of the initial one. The original TPM may be applied to pure Mode I cracking, whereas the proposed MTPM is able to also capture the local mixed Mode cracking at the peak load, that may occur in composite materials such as PBs.

In the present paper, the size-effect independence of fracture toughness for a commercial PB (provided by the University Politehnica of Timisoara, Romania) is investigated when the MTPM is employed to measure such a parameter. To such an aim, notched PB beams with different geometric sizes are tested under three-point bending. The computed value of fracture toughness is then compared with the experimental results reported in Ref.[33], related to the same composite material.

The paper is structured as follows: firstly, the material and testing methods employed to compute the fracture toughness and density are presented in Section 2. Then, the results obtained are shown and commented in Section 3. In Section 4, conclusions are summarised.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 PB specimens

The tested specimens have been made by cutting prismatic samples from commercial PB panels composed by five layers (**Figure 1**): the core, two faces, and two melamine coatings. Three types of panels (named PB16, PB25 and PB36 in the following) are examined, differing from each other for the layers thickness values. The nominal thickness values of the panels, B , are listed in **Table 1**, together with the corresponding ratios between each layer thickness and B .

Table 1

As can be noted, the ratios B_c/B , B_f/B and B_{Core}/B are not constant by varying the panel thickness, B , and consequently the density is not a constant although the material is the same. This is a limitation imposed by the industrial production.

The material forming direction (that is, the orientation given to the wood particles during the production process) is shown in **Figure 1**.

According to both the TPM [35-37] and the MTPM [34], the specimen sizes are function of its width, B (corresponding to the thickness of the panel,): depth $W=2B$, span $S=8B$, and notch depth $a_0=2/3B$ with notch width $<1.45mm$ (**Figure 2(a)**).

Figure 2

In order to analyse the size-effect on fracture toughness, six specimens for each panel type are tested:

- six specimens (named PB16-X, where X identifies the specimen number) with nominal width B equal to 16mm;
- six specimens (named PB25-X) with B equal to 25mm;

- six specimens (named PB36-X) with B equal to 36mm.

For each specimen, the nominal values of both length L and span S are listed in **Table 2** together with the mean values of depth W , width B and notch depth a_0 .

Table 2

Before testing, all specimens have been stored in laboratory at 20°C and 65% relative humidity.

2.2 PB fracture toughness

Three-point bending tests on notched specimens have been performed through the universal testing machine Instron 8862 available at the 'Testing Laboratory of Material and Structures', University of Parma, Italy (**Figure 2(b)**). The tests are carried out according to both TPM [35] and RILEM Recommendations [36,37] under Crack Mouth Opening Displacement (CMOD) control, by employing a clip gauge. It was experimentally proved that, for wood and wood-based composites, high values of CMOD rate cause an increase in the value of fracture toughness [18]. Therefore, in order to make the test results CMOD rate-independent, the CMOD rate ν is computed through the following equation, suggested by the ASTM D1037 standard [38]:

$$\nu = \frac{zS^2}{6W} = 0.112B \quad (1)$$

where z is the CMOD unit rate per minute, here taken equal to 0.021 in order to achieve the peak load P_{max} in about ten minutes. Consequently, the CMOD rate v is not assumed to be constant, since it depends on the specimen sizes S and W . In the present study: $v=1.8mm/min$, $2.8mm/min$, $4.0mm/min$ for specimen series PB16-X, PB25-X, PB36-X, respectively.

The applied load P is measured by means of a load cell of 100 kN and accuracy up to 0.02%. As is shown in **Figure 2(c)**, each specimen is monotonically loaded. After achieving the peak load P_{max} , the post-peak stage follows and, when the load is equal to about 95% of P_{max} , the specimen is fully unloaded (up to a load value equal to about zero) by proceeding under load control. Finally, the specimen is reloaded up to failure under CMOD control with the same initial CMOD rate.

By exploiting the experimental measurements in terms of peak load (P_{max}), initial (C_i) and unloading (C_u) linear elastic compliances (see a typical load against CMOD curve in **Figure 2(c)**), the elastic modulus E and the fracture toughness $K_{(I+II)C}^S$ (also named critical Stress-Intensity Factor for mixed mode) are computed according to the Modified Two-Parameter Model (MTPM). Details are reported in the Appendix and in Refs **[34,39-41]**.

Note that during stable propagation (that is, prior to the peak load is achieved) the crack starting from the notch root may experience a kinked path. Some examples are shown in **Figure 3**. This

means that cracks are subjected to mixed mode loading (Mode I together with Mode II) although the remote loading is Mode I loading. This is due to PB heterogeneity caused by randomly distributed wood particles. By employing the MTPM, fracture toughness is estimated by taking into account the crack kinking. The TPM, instead, evaluates fracture toughness by considering stable crack propagation under pure Mode I, thus overestimating the actual value of such a parameter (as is detailed in the Appendix).

Figure 3

2.3 PB density

Particleboard specimens obtained from panels with different thickness values present different values of density. As matter of fact, by increasing the total thickness of the panel, the thickness of the core usually increases more than the thicknesses of the faces, with a consequent reduction of the material density.

Since it is well-known that the fracture toughness of wood and wood-based composites is strongly dependent on density [18], the density of each tested specimen has to be measured in order to correlate the computed fracture toughness with the corresponding density value.

The density ρ of each specimen is determined according to the ASTM D1037 standard [38]. The specimens are weighted immediately after testing; then, the oven-dry weight is obtained after drying the specimens at $103\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, until constant weight is attained with an

accuracy of about 0.5%. The density is evaluated as the ratio between the dry-weight and the corresponding specimen volume computed by taking into account the actual sizes of each specimen. The values of density ρ determined for all specimen series are listed in **Table 2**.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Load-CMOD curves

The results deduced by applying the MTPM are listed in **Table 3** for each tested specimen. In more detail, the measured values of peak load P_{max} and the computed results in terms of elastic modulus E and the critical SIF for mixed mode, $K_{(I+II)C}^S$, are displayed.

Table 3

Figure 4 shows the experimental load-CMOD curves for specimens PB16-1, PB25-1 and PB36-1. Only one curve for each specimen series is plotted since, for the same nominal sizes, the experimental load-CMOD curves are quite similar to each other.

Figure 4

It can be remarked that the CMOD at the peak load ranges from about 0.388mm (for specimen No. PB16-1) to about 0.573mm (for specimen No. PB36-1). Moreover, a significant load bearing capability in the post-peak behaviour can be noticed even for large values of CMOD (that is, values greater than 1mm).

The mean value μ and standard deviation σ of P_{max} , E and $K_{(I+II)C}^S$ for each specimen series are listed in **Table 4**.

Table 4

By focusing the attention on the mean value of the peak load P_{max} , it can be observed that, by taking as reference the mean value related to the specimen series PB16-X, the mean value increases with the specimens sizes of about 126% for specimen series PB25-X, and 232% for PB36-X. Moreover, the standard deviation ranges from 0.042 kN to 0.068 kN, highlighting a low data dispersion.

The mean value of the elastic modulus E is about constant, since μ ranges from a minimum value of 2012 MPa (for PB36-X) to a maximum value of 2225 MPa (for PB25-X), with a maximum variation of about 10%.

The mean value of fracture toughness $K_{(I+II)C}^S$ ranges from a minimum of 1.069 MPa(m)^{0.5} (for PB36-X) to a maximum of 1.253 MPa(m)^{0.5} (for PB25-X), with a maximum variation of about 15%. Therefore, it is not possible to claim that the fracture toughness obtained from the MTPM is size-independent, since it does not show constant values by varying the specimen sizes. Such a behaviour may be explained by taking into account that fracture toughness depends on the material density which is not constant for the different specimen series examined (see Section 3.2).

3.2 Density

As is highlighted in Section 2.3, density is not constant for the commercial panel examined: as a matter of fact, by increasing the panel thickness, the thickness of the core (usually characterised by a lower density) does not proportionally increase with respect to the thickness of the faces (characterised by a higher density). By observing **Table 1**, the ratio between the core thickness and the faces thickness is not constant, but it is equal to 4.5, 6.6 and 7.2 for PB16-X, PB25-X and PB36-X series, respectively, with consequent reduction of the specimens density.

By taking as reference the PB16-X series, the decrease of density is equal to about 3% for PB25-X series and equal to about 10.3% for PB36-X series.

The moisture content, computed (in percent) as the difference between initial and final weights over the final weight, is constant since it is equal to about 7.8% for all the specimens.

3.3 Fracture toughness index

In order to evaluate the dependence or not of the fracture toughness on the specimen sizes, such a parameter should be referred to specimens characterised by the same value of density ρ .

Therefore, a fracture toughness index I_K is proposed by the authors, defined as follows:

$$I_K = \frac{K_{(I+II)C}^S}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

Such an index is computed for each specimen. The mean values of I_K are equal to $1.849 \text{ MPam}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$, $2.042 \text{ MPam}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$, and $1.945 \text{ MPam}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$ for specimen series PB16-X, PB25-X, and PB36-X, respectively, whereas the corresponding standard deviations are equal to $0.09 \text{ MPam}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$, $0.12 \text{ MPam}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$, and $0.05 \text{ MPam}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$, respectively.

The above values are plotted in **Figure 5** for each specimen series together with the corresponding error bars (one standard deviation above and below the mean value). A careful examination of **Figure 5**, in terms of error bars, suggests that the difference between mean values can be considered as a result of aleatory variability and/or measurement errors, that is, the fracture toughness index (fracture toughness per density unit) is size-independent. As matter of fact, by subtracting one standard deviation from the mean value of I_K related to both PB25-X and PB36-X series, the result obtained is almost equal to the mean value of I_K related to PB16-X series.

Figure 5

As a consequence, it can be deduced that PB fracture toughness is size-independent, since the fracture toughness variation obtained is due to density, not to specimen sizes.

3.4 Comparison with literature data

The mean value of I_K is here compared with that computed using other fracture toughness measurements on the same commercial PB, which are available in Ref. [33].

Marsavina et al. [33] have performed tests on two specimen types:

- (i) Single-edge notched bend specimens subjected to three-point bending, for Mode I fracture toughness ($K_{IC} = 0.87 \text{ MPa(m)}^{0.5}$);
- (ii) Compact shear specimens, for Mode II fracture toughness ($K_{IIC} = 0.62 \text{ MPa(m)}^{0.5}$).

An equivalent fracture toughness may be defined by using the Tanaka's equation [42]:

$$K_{IC,eq} = \sqrt[4]{K_{IC}^4 + 8K_{IIC}^4} \quad (3)$$

where $K_{IC,eq}$ is equal to $1.151 \text{ MPa(m)}^{0.5}$.

By considering the density of about 600 kg/m^3 [33], the fracture toughness index I_K defined in Eq. (4) is equal to $1.912 \text{ MPa m}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$. Note that the mean value of the I_K results deduced in the previous subsection ($1.849 \text{ MPa m}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$, $2.042 \text{ MPa m}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$, and $1.945 \text{ MPa m}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$) is equal to $1.945 \text{ MPa m}^{7/2}/\text{kg}$ and, therefore, the difference between such a mean value and the value of I_K determined using the data reported in Ref. [33] is lower than 3%.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The present paper has been dedicated to prove the size-effect independence of particleboard fracture toughness when the MTPM is used to measure such a parameter. To apply such a model, three-point bending tests on notched specimens characterised by different sizes have been performed.

The main conclusions of the present research work are hereafter summarised:

- An increase of the specimen width causes a reduction of density. Such a density reduction is of about 10% with the specimen width ranging from 16mm to 36mm.
- The peak load increases by increasing the specimen sizes: the increase is equal to about 126% for the PB25-X series and 232% for the PB36-X series, by taking as reference the PB16-X series. The elastic modulus, instead, is about constant;
- A fracture toughness index has been defined in order to compare the $K_{(I+II)C}^S$ values independent of the density variation. It has been observed that I_K , and consequently the fracture toughness computed through the MTPM, is size-independent;
- The improvement due to the MTPM application is to measure the critical SIF under mixed mode through a single test (that is, a three-point bending test), whereas the equivalent fracture toughness (see Eq. (3)) requires two different experimental tests.

APPENDIX

The present Appedix is related to the determination of $K_{(I+II)C}^S$ according to the Modified Two Parameter Model. The geometry of the specimens is presented in Section 2.1, whereas the testing method is described in Section 2.2.

Firstly, for each tested specimen, the initial compliance C_i is computed from the corresponding load-CMOD curve (see Figure 2(c)), and used to determine the elastic modulus E :

$$E = \frac{6S a_0 V(\alpha_0)}{C_i W^2 B} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where the parameter V is given by

$$V(\alpha_0) = 0.76 - 2.28\alpha_0 + 3.87\alpha_0^2 - 2.04\alpha_0^3 + \frac{0.66}{(1-\alpha_0)^2} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

being $\alpha_0 = a_0/W$.

Then, two cases can experimentally occur in terms of stable crack propagation before the maximum load P_{max} is achieved, that is:

- (a) the crack kinking angle θ is quite constant along the propagation crack path (see Figure A.1);
- (b) the crack kinking angle θ is not constant along the propagation crack path (see Figure A.2).

Figure A.1

Figure A.2

In case (a), the effective crack length $\underline{a} = a_0 + (a_1 + a_2)\cos\theta$ is computed from the following equation by using an iterative procedure:

$$E = \frac{6S}{C_u W^2 B} \left\{ a_0 V\left(\frac{a_0}{W}\right) + \left[\cos^6 \frac{\theta}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\theta}{2} \cos^4 \frac{\theta}{2} \right] \left[(a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta) V\left(\frac{a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta}{W}\right) - a_0 V\left(\frac{a_0}{W}\right) \right] + \left[\cos^3 \theta + \sin^2 \theta \cos\theta \right] \left[(a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta + a_2 \cos\theta) V\left(\frac{a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta + a_2 \cos\theta}{W}\right) - (a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta) V\left(\frac{a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta}{W}\right) \right] \right\} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where $a_1 = 0.3a_0$, the unloading compliance C_u is computed from the corresponding load-CMOD curve (see Figure 2(c)), and a_2 is the unknown quantity to be determined. Note that, when the fracture surface is not plane, the mean value of θ is determined by averaging the values related to front and back side of the specimen.

If the value of a_2 from Eq.(A.3) is negative, it means that $\underline{a} = a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta$, and then the unknown quantity a_1 is computed from the following equation by using an iterative procedure:

$$E = \frac{6S}{C_u W^2 B} \left\{ a_0 V\left(\frac{a_0}{W}\right) + \left[\cos^6 \frac{\theta}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\theta}{2} \cos^4 \frac{\theta}{2} \right] \left[(a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta) V\left(\frac{a_0 + a_1 \cos\theta}{W}\right) - a_0 V\left(\frac{a_0}{W}\right) \right] \right\} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Finally, the critical stress-intensity factor $K_{(I+II)C}^S$ is computed as:

$$K_{(I+II)C}^S = \frac{3P_{\max}S}{2W^2 B} \sqrt{\pi [a_0 + (a_1 + a_2)\cos\theta]} f(\alpha) \quad \alpha = \frac{a_0 + (a_1 + a_2)\cos\theta}{W} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

when $a_1 = 0.3a_0$, whereas it is computed as

$$K_{(I+II)C}^S = \frac{3P_{\max}S}{2W^2 B} \sqrt{\pi [a_0 + (a_1 + a_2)\cos\theta]} f(\alpha) \quad \alpha = \frac{a_0 + (a_1 + a_2)\cos\theta}{W} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

when $a_1 < 0.3a_0$, being:

$$f(\alpha) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1.99 - \alpha(1-\alpha)(2.15 - 3.93\alpha + 2.70\alpha^2)}{(1+2\alpha)(1-\alpha)^{3/2}} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

In case (b), the orientation θ of the first deflected segment $i+1$ (with $i=1,\dots,N$, where N is a positive integer) such that $l_{i+1}>l_i$ is taken into account in Eqs (A.3)-(A.6).

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**SIZE-EFFECT INDEPENDENCE OF
PARTICLEBOARD FRACTURE TOUGHNESS**

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1. Particleboard layers: B_{Core} is the core thickness, B_f is the faces thickness, B_c is the coatings thickness, and B is the total panel thickness.

Table 1. Nominal thickness values for each type of PB panel examined, and dimensionless nominal thickness values of corresponding layers.

1. TYPE	PANEL	B [mm]	B_c/B	B_f/B	B_{Core}/B
PB16		16	0.031	0.144	0.650
PB25		25	0.020	0.112	0.736
PB36		36	0.014	0.106	0.761

Figure 2. Three-point bending test: (a) specimen geometry and loading configuration, (b) testing setup, and (c) typical load against Crack Mouth Opening Displacement ($CMOD$) curve for the tested specimens.

Table 2. Mean values of specimen sizes and density, for each specimen series examined.

2. SERIES	SPECIMEN	W [mm]	B [mm]	S [mm]	L [mm]	a_0 [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]
PB16-X		31.83	16.34	128	160	11.17	616
PB25-X		49.90	25.24	200	250	16.65	599
PB36-X		72.17	36.13	288	379	25.05	552

Figure 3. Crack path for one specimen for each series (front side and back side): (a-a') PB16-1; (b-b') PB25-1; (c-c') PB36-1.

Table 3. Peak load P_{max} , elastic modulus E , and critical SIF $K_{(I+II)C}^S$ for mixed mode, for each tested specimen.

SPECIMEN No.	P_{max} [kN]	E [MPa]	$K_{(I+II)C}^S$ [MPa(m) ^{0.5}]
PB16-1	0.460	2119.61	1.249
PB16-2	0.384	1822.40	1.078
PB16-3	0.366	1987.51	1.054
PB16-4	0.352	2083.35	1.059
PB16-5	0.377	2062.53	1.137
PB16-6	0.427	2203.09	1.125
PB25-1	0.919	2302.80	1.242
PB25-2	0.914	2295.07	1.309
PB25-3	0.991	2256.97	1.317
PB25-4	0.800	2100.98	1.138
PB25-5	0.901	2134.25	1.220
PB25-6	0.956	2264.64	1.290
PB36-1	1.416	2136.63	1.090
PB36-2	1.296	2092.07	1.045
PB36-3	1.396	1810.16	1.083
PB36-4	1.239	2041.06	1.076
PB36-5	1.328	2079.57	1.073
PB36-6	1.321	1913.78	1.047

Figure 4. Load against Crack Mouth Opening Displacement (CMOD) for specimens Nos PB16-1, PB25-1, and PB36-1.

Table 4. Mean value μ and standard deviation σ of P_{max} , E and $K_{(I+II)C}^S$, for the three specimen series examined.

3. SERIES	SPECIMEN	P_{max} [kN]		E [MPa]		$K_{(I+II)C}^S$ [MPa(m) ^{0.5}]	
		μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
PB16-X		0.394	0.042	2046.42	118.03	1.117	0.082
PB25-X		0.913	0.068	2225.79	94.02	1.253	0.073
PB36-X		1.332	0.065	2012.21	124.69	1.069	0.019

Figure 5. Mean value of fracture toughness index I_K against specimen series. The horizontal dashed line corresponds to the mean value of I_K for the specimen series PB16-X.

Figure A.1 Case (a): the crack kinking angle, θ , is a constant.

Figure A.2 Case (b): the crack kinking angle, θ , is not constant.